

Measuring Tourist Satisfaction by Accessibility: The Case of Taman Wisata Alam Gunung Pancar Destination

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Abstract:- The tourism sector is a leading sector in several developed countries. This is because people's need for travel has become a primary need. However, the COVID-19 pandemic that occurred in early 2020 had a major impact on the global economy. This has an impact on the number of tourist visits globally, which has decreased by 73% in 2020. The pattern of tourist travel after the COVID-19 pandemic has also changed where travel is more directed towards alternative tourism such as nature tourism. The development of tourist destinations can be done in terms of attractions, amenities, and accessibility. However, accessibility is often forgotten in the development of a destination, even though accessibility is one of the factors of tourist satisfaction. Accessibility to tourist destinations Gunung Pancar natural tourism park is still constrained by the distance and time that must be traveled from the city of Bogor. In addition, road directions to tourist destinations are still limited. Based on the above background, the purpose of this study is to measure tourist satisfaction through accessibility to tourist destinations of Mount Pancar Natural Tourism Park in Bogor Regency.

The research method used is a quantitative approach with a simple regression analysis tool. Respondents used in this study were tourists who had visited the Mount Pancar natural tourism park. The results show that accessibility can be used to measure tourist satisfaction because it is proven that accessibility has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction. Future research that can be done is to analyze aspects of the development of tourist destinations which consist of attractions, amenities, and accessibility, which aspects have the most influence on tourist satisfaction in Gunung Pancar Natural Tourism Park, so that managers can focus on aspects that are still not good based on tourist perspective.

Keyword:- Accessibility, Tourist Satisfaction, Nature Tourism

I. INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector is currently the leading sector for the development of a country. The tourism industry is a human activity that travels with various activities related to tourist destinations (A.Yoeti & Gunadi, 2013). Tourism in

developed countries has become a leading sector. People's need for travel to get relaxation, curiosity, experience, knowledge, and entertainment has become a necessity. The impact of this routine of daily activities is to release fatigue and boredom with traveling. Based on Brokaj (2014), many developing countries promote their tourism because tourism has the potential to create jobs, increase per capita income, and increase foreign exchange and government income. Data quoted from UNWTO (2017) Figure 1 shows that the tourism sector has become a leading sector for world economic growth. Tourism can be categorized into the world's largest industrial group, as it accounts for about 8% of exports of goods and services. Tourism is also the largest contributor to international trade. If it is known that the tourism sector contributes an average of 10% to Gross Domestic Growth (GDP) in each country, then 1 in 10 people must work in the tourism sector. In addition, the level of world tourist arrivals and international tourism receipts from and to various countries has increased every year, as reported by UNWTO (2017). However, the COVID-19 pandemic that occurred in early 2020 had a major impact on the global economy. This situation has the worst impact on the tourism sector in history (Gössling, 2015; Hall et al., 2020; Sheresheva et al., 2020). All tourism activities cannot run according to the wishes of various parties in the tourism industry. Contact restrictions occur globally in various sectors, so that the economic loss is very large. (Duarte Alonso et al., 2020). This has an impact on the number of tourist visits globally, which has decreased by 73% in 2020, but changes occur in 2021, when there is an increase in the number of tourist visits. This gives great hope to the tourism sector, so that it can adapt to conditions after the COVID-19 pandemic.

(OECD, 2020) The pattern of tourist travel after the COVID-19 pandemic has changed such that travel is more directed to alternative tourism. Alternative types of tourism activities that are oriented to nature tourism are more in demand, such as mountain climbing (hiking), adventure tourism, and trekking. Indonesia is famous for its biodiversity and beautiful landscapes. Bogor Regency, which is located in West Java Province, has natural attractions that are famous for their natural beauty, namely the Mount Pancar Nature Tourism Park. Data on domestic and foreign tourist arrivals in 2020 is shown in Figure 2, where the number of tourist visits has increased from August to December.

Fig 1 Number of tourists in Mount Pancar Natural Park in 2020

Source: management Mount Pancar Natural Park

The increase in the number of tourists to natural tourism Gunung Pancar natural tourism park is a benchmark for the development of natural tourism Gunung Pancar Natural Tourism Park. The development of a destination is carried out on the aspects of attractions, amenities, and accessibility (A.Yoeti & Gunadi, 2013). Accessibility is often forgotten in the development of a destination, even though accessibility is a determining factor for tourist satisfaction. Tourist satisfaction with tourist destinations is related to the travel experience consisting of accommodation, tourist attractions, and accessib (Ramseook-Munhurrun et al., 2015). Based on Diwangkara et al (2020) Important factors related to accessibility are directions, airports, terminals, travel costs, time taken, frequency of transportation to tourist destinations and others.

Rossadi & Widayati (2018) Accessibility is a means of infrastructure that can provide convenience for someone who wants to use it when travelling. The condition of the road to the tourist attraction is very important because tourists who visit will pay attention to the condition of the road. The condition of the road, as well as the distance traveled and the short travel time to the tourist location, will increase tourist interest. Therefore, it is important for managers to have the ability to know and understand the wishes of visitors to a tourist spot so that they can continue to adjust and make improvements so that business continuity will continue (Kusumawardhani, 2022). Accessibility to tourist destinations Gunung Pancar natural tourism park is still constrained by the distance and time that must be traveled from the city of Bogor. In addition, road directions to tourist destinations are still limited, so tourists who will access the road to the natural tourist destination of Mount Pancar will have difficulty knowing the exact location of this tour. Based on the above background, the purpose of this study is to measure tourist satisfaction through accessibility to tourist destinations of Gunung Pancar Natural Tourism Park in Bogor Regency.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Accessibility

One of the important components in tourism activities is the accessibility or smoothness of the community or tourists from place to place. The movement can be within close or long distances. Accessibility refers to the means and infrastructure needed to get to a destination. Road access, the

availability of transportation facilities, and road signs are important aspects for a destination. (Rusvitasari & Solikhin, 2014). Dimensions of accessibility are alternative roads, road conditions, distance traveled, travel time, and means of transportation (Susumaningsih, 2020). Good road access is not enough without the availability of transportation facilities. For tourists, public facilities and facilities are very important because they provide convenience for tourists to reach tourist destinations without a travel agent. Therefore, accessibility is crucial for the development of a tourist destination. Accessibility does not only concern the ease of transportation for tourists to reach a tourist spot or a certain destination, but also the time required to follow signs directing to tourist sites and other related devices.

B. Tourist satisfaction

A person's feelings of pleasure or disappointment arise after comparing the performance (outcome) of the product they purchased to the expected performance (result) (Kotler, 2012). Meanwhile, tourist satisfaction is the extent to which the performance of a tourist destination can meet tourist expectations. If the performance of a tourist destination is lower than the expectations of tourists, then tourists will feel dissatisfied, and vice versa, if the performance of a tourist destination exceeds expectations, tourists will feel satisfied. Tourist satisfaction with tourist destinations is related to the travel experience, which includes accommodation, accessibility, and tourist attractions offered. (Ramseook-Munhurrun et al., 2015). On the other hand, tourist satisfaction is defined as a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that comes from the comparison between expectations and real or actual service performance (Nelwan & Areros, William Agustinus; Tampi, 2016). The indicators for assessing customer satisfaction are the suitability of expectations, interest in reusing, and willingness to recommend (Aspiani, 2017)

III. METHOD

The research method in writing this scientific article uses quantitative methods by presenting the results of regression analysis. The sample obtained as many as 100 respondents was obtained from visitors to the tourist area at Gunung Pancar Nature Tourism Park. The accessibility and satisfaction use a Likert scale with a score of 5 points Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Neutral (3), Agree (4), and Strongly Agree (5) are the options. The dimensions of

accessibility consist of Alternative Roads, Road Conditions, Mileage, Travel Time, and Transportation Facilities (Susumaningsih, 2020). The dimensions of tourist satisfaction are Conformity of Expectations, Interest in revisiting, and Willingness to Recommend (Aspiani, 2017). The hypothesis in this study is as follows:

H0: accessibility has no effect on tourist satisfaction

H1: accessibility affects tourist satisfaction

IV. THE RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The general description of the characteristics of the respondents includes the socio-economic and travel description of the respondents. Based on gender, there were more male respondents (52%) than females (48%). Then, the

age of the respondents who visited the most was in the age range of 20 to 30 years (79%), age less than 20 years (18%), and the age range of 30 to 40 years (3%). This shows that tourists who come to the natural tourism park of Mount Pancar are still at a young age. Based on the amount of expenditure per month, respondents whose expenses are less than IDR 1,000,000 (23%), in the range of IDR 1,000,000 to IDR 2,000,000 (27%), IDR 2,000,000 to IDR 3,000,000 (25%), IDR 3,000,000 to IDR 4,000,000 (12%), and more than IDR 4,000,000 (13%). The frequency of respondents visiting Gunung Pancar natural tourism park was once (48%), twice (25%), three times (11%), and more than three times (16%). Based on the purpose of visiting, the respondent's purpose is to travel (91%), for observation (3%), for work (2%), and others (4%).

Table 1 Characteristics of visitors

Characters	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	52	52%
	Female	48	48%
Age	<20	18	18%
	20-30	79	79%
	30-40	3	3%
Expense per month	< Rp 1.000.000	23	23%
	IDR 1.000.000-IDR 2.000.000	27	27%
	IDR 2.000.000-IDR 3.000.000	25	25%
	IDR 3.000.000-IDR 4.000.000	12	12%
	>IDR 4.000.000	13	13%
Frequency of visits	1 time	48	48%
	2 time	25	25%
	3 time	11	11%
	>3 time	16	16%
Purpose of visit	Travel	91	91%
	Observation	3	3%
	Work	2	2%
	Other	4	4%

The accessibility variable (X) has five dimensions with 10 indicators, where each dimension has indicators that are developed into questions. The number of respondents who answered this question was 100. Judging from the 10 questions above, it can be seen that the average value of question item number X1.8, namely the travel time dimension, has the highest average, namely 4.01. While the smallest average value is in the question item number X1.10, namely the dimension means of transportation with a value of 2.79. Of all the dimensions and indicators of the accessibility

variable question, the highest mean value is the X1.8 indicator, with a value of 4.01. In the travel time dimension, the highest average value occurs because the time traveled by tourists is proportional to the beauty of the Nature Tourism Park. Gunung Pancar, and the lowest mean value is the question indicator X.1.10 with a value of 2.79 The lowest average value is because it is easier for tourists to use private vehicles rather than use public transportation.

Table 2 Accessibility

Accessibility indicator (X)	Description
X1.1.	The ease condition of the road to get to the destination
X1.2	Easy accessibility
X1.3	Ease of finding alternative routes
X1.4	Ease of accessibility through alternative roads compared to the main road
X1.5	Mileage to the destination
X1.6	The distance traveled is in line with the expectations of the natural beauty of the destination.
X1.7	Travel time
X1.8	The atmosphere at the destination is in line with expectations and travel time to the tourist attraction.

X1.9	Ease of finding public transportation to the destination
X1.10	Ease of using means of transportation compared to private vehicles

The Tourist Satisfaction Variable (Y) has 3 dimensions with 6 statement indicators, where each dimension has indicators that are developed into questions. The tourist satisfaction variable has an average value (mean) between 3.51 and 4.00 with a standard deviation of 0.65 to 0.99. Of all the dimensions and indicators of the Y variable question, the highest mean value is the Y1.6 indicator, with a value of 4.00 on the willingness to recommend dimension. The highest average value occurs because tourists are satisfied with the

beauty of the Gunung Pancar Nature Park, so they can recommend it to others. So that other people can travel to Gunung Pancar Natural Park, and for the lowest mean value, namely the Y1.1 question indicator with a value of 3.60, the lowest average value occurs because tourists are not satisfied with the accessibility of going to Gunung Pancar Nature Park, which has been mentioned in several question indicators and the dimensions are X variables.

Tourist Satisfaction Indicator	Description
Y1.1	Satisfaction on accessibility to the destination
Y1.2	Accessibility to destinations in line with expectations of natural beauty
Y1.3	Satisfaction on easy-to-find transportation facilities to the destination
Y1.4	Satisfaction on accessibility to the destination, makes you want to visit again
Y1.5	Recommendation the destination to other people
Y1.6	Satisfaction with natural beauty thereby promoting the destination

Table 3 Tourist Satisfaction

➤ *Validity and Reliability Test*

Based on the results of the validity test of the accessibility variable and tourist satisfaction, the corrected item-total correlation value is greater than 0.3, so it can be said that these items can be used to measure the research variables. Meanwhile, the reliability test of the accessibility and tourist satisfaction variables has a value on Cronbach's Alpha of 0.831 and 0.849, respectively, where these two variables have a Cronbach's Alpha greater than 0.6, so it can be stated that the accessibility and tourist satisfaction variables used for research are reliable.

➤ *Normality test*

The following table shows the results of the normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, where the data can be said to be normal, provided that if the significant value is > 0.05 then the data distribution is normal. On the other hand, if the significant value is < 0.05, then the data distribution is not normal. The results of the normality test on the tourist satisfaction variable are shown based on a significance value (ASYMP.Sig – 2-Tailed) of 0.323 (0.323 > 0.05), it can be said that the residual value is normally distributed.

➤ *Heteroscedasticity Test*

A heteroscedasticity test was conducted to see the data variance, whether there were symptoms of heteroscedasticity or not. There were no symptoms of heteroscedasticity,

commonly called homoscedasticity. Based on the results of the heteroscedasticity test, the significance value (Sig.) for the accessibility variable (X) is 1,000. This is in accordance with the basis for decision making in the Glejser test, where the significance value of the variables in the table is greater than 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no symptom of heteroscedasticity in this data.

➤ *Simple Linear Regression Test*

The simple linear regression equation model is seen from the value of unstandardized coefficients as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta X$$

$$Y = 4.379 + 0.514 X$$

Based on a simple linear regression equation, the constant value (α) is 4.379, meaning that if there is a change in the value of the accessibility variable (X) of 0, then the tourist satisfaction variable (Y) is worth 4.379. The regression coefficient (β) of the accessibility variable (X) is 0.514, meaning that if the tourist satisfaction value gets an additional 1 unit, then the accessibility value of Mount Pancar Nature Park will increase by 0.514. This regression coefficient is positive, so that it can be said that there is a unidirectional relationship between the role of accessibility and tourist satisfaction.

Table 4 Simple Linear Regression Test

Table 6. Partial Test Results (T Test)

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	4.379	1.398		3.132	.002
Total_X	.514	.039	.801	13.254	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Total_y

Source: SPSS 20, 2021

➤ *R Correlation Test*

Based on table 5, it can be seen that the correlation value or R is 0.801. This shows that the accessibility variable has a very strong relationship with the tourist satisfaction variable because the correlation value R is 0.801 to 1. Then to find out the magnitude of the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable can be seen from the R Square coefficient value obtained, which is 0.642. This demonstrates that the independent variable, accessibility (X), contributes 64.2 percent to the dependent variable, tourist satisfaction (Y). Other variables not investigated in this study influence the remaining 35.8 percent.

Table 5 R Correlation Test Results

Source: SPSS 20, 2021

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.801 ^a	.642	.638	2.181

a. Predictors: (Constant), Total_X

Partial Test (T Test)

Based on table 6, it is known that the tcount value of the Accessibility variable is 13,254, using a significance level of 0.05, the ttable value is 1,984 (based on the calculation $df = 100 - 2 = 98$) which means that the tcount value of the Accessibility variable is greater than the ttable value, namely $13,254 > 1,984$, so it can be concluded that Accessibility (X) has an effect on Tourist Satisfaction (Y). Then the significance value of the Accessibility variable (X) is 0.000 which is less than 0.05, then the H1 hypothesis is accepted, indicating that the Accessibility variable (X) has a significant effect on the Tourist Satisfaction variable (Y).

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	4.379	1.398		3.132	.002
Total_X	.514	.039	.801	13.254	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Total_y

V. CONCLUSION

Mount Pancar Nature Park is one of the tourist attractions that has natural beauty in the form of mountains and pine forests so that it can attract tourists to visit Mount Pancar Nature Park, both domestic and foreign tourists. Tourist satisfaction can be measured based on accessibility to Gunung Pancar natural tourism park. Accessibility has been proven to affect tourist satisfaction in the Gunung Pancar natural tourism park. Therefore, it is important for tourism managers to consider accessibility to Gunung Alam tourist park. Based on the results of the research, the problems that still occur related to accessibility are that there is no special road to the Mount Pancar natural tourism park, including signs to the destination, so that tourists often have difficulty reaching the destination. Managers need to pay attention to this so that tourists can easily reach their destinations. Future research that can be carried out is based on aspects of developing tourist destinations, namely attractions, amenities, and accessibility. Which aspects have the most influence on tourist satisfaction at Gunung Pancar Natural Park, so that managers can develop aspects that are still a problem in Gunung Pancar Natural Tourism Park. based on the perspective of tourist satisfaction.

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